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Impact of nano-dopants on the mechanical and physical properties of magnesium oxychloride cement composites – Experimental assessment

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ABSTRACT

The importance of the reduction of the World's CO₂ emissions due to their non-negligible contribution to climate change is inevitable. As the Portland cement (PC) industry is one of the main contributors to the overall volume of CO₂ emissions produced over the World, a sustainable PC substitute must be implemented. Previous scientific studies suggest that magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) – an eco-friendly binder based on reactive magnesia – could be a suitable alternative. This contribution studies the influence of various nano-dopants on the mechanical and physical properties of MOC-based composites. The nano-dopants introduced to the MOC composite were the following: multi-walled carbon nanotubes, oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, graphene nanoplatelets, and alumina nanosheets. Ahead of the composite preparation, the nano-dopants were analysed with a wide spectrum of analytical methods to study their composition and microstructure in detail. The used amount of nano-dopant was 1.0 wt%, relative to the cement paste weight. After a curing period of 28 days, the prepared composite samples underwent a comprehensive analysis of their microstructure, phase, and chemical composition, as well as micro- and macrostructural parameters and mechanical properties. Additionally, the research studied the effects of nano-dopants on the hygric properties and water resistance of the MOC composites after 24-h immersion in water. The findings revealed a noteworthy increase in mechanical parameters with the addition of nano-dopants. The highest compressive strength of 85.4 MPa was obtained for the MOC composite enriched with the addition of oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes. MOC doped with alumina nanosheets exhibited the highest value in flexural strength (20.99 MPa) and dynamic modulus of elasticity (38.85 GPa) measurements. The resistance of MOC composites to deterioration in water was also improved by all the implemented nano-dopants. The softening coefficient determined for samples immersed in water for 24 h varied from 62.7 to 74.8%. The best resistance to water degradation was obtained for MOC with alumina nanosheets, which showed a softening coefficient value about 23.2% higher than that of the reference sample. Thus, the incorporation of nano-materials as functional nano-dopants in MOC-based composites shows promising opportunities in the improvement of both mechanical properties and water resistance, contributing to the development of environmentally sustainable building materials.

1. Introduction

Magnesium oxychloride cement is a presumed eco-friendly alternative to PC. Its environmental benefits compared to PC come from its lower processing temperature (800 °C for MOC and 1450 °C for PC [1]) and therefore lower energy consumption, and also its ability to sequester CO₂ from the atmosphere while forming chlorocarbonate phase chlorartinite [2–4]. Power et al. presented in their study, that MOC-based boards can offset up to 40% of the emissions released during their production by the process of CO₂ sequestra-

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Table 1
Mixture composition of prepared samples (g), NANO stands for five different types of nano-dopants (CNT, CNT-Ox, G, GO, and ANS).

Sample	MgO	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	H ₂ O	NANO	PG1	PG2	PG3
M-REF	650.0	655.7	406.8	–	650.0	650.0	650.0
M-NANO	650.0	655.7	406.8	17.1	650.0	650.0	650.0

Fig. 1. SEM (left) and TEM (right) micrographs of all nano-dopants.

Fig. 2. EDS elemental maps of all nano-dopants.

Table 2

Chemical composition of CNT, CNT-Ox, GO, G and ANS according to EDS in wt.%.

Nano-dopant	C	O	Ni	S	Si	Al	Mn	K
CNT	97.7	2.3	–	–	–	–	–	–
CNT-Ox	96.9	1.9	1.2	–	–	–	–	–
GO	62.9	27.5	–	7.9	–	–	1.2	0.5
G	92.9	6.6	–	–	0.5	–	–	–
ANS	7.2	38.5	–	–	–	54.3	–	–

Fig. 3. Photograph of prepared cement composites M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS samples.

Fig. 4. Micrographs of prepared composites from optical microscope.

tion [5]. In its most promising and researched form, MOC phase 5 ($Mg_3(OH)_5Cl \cdot 4H_2O$), it provides mechanical properties similar or even superior to those of PC with some specific properties such as fire resistance, fast setting, and an increased ability to accommodate a very large amount of filler of various origin including waste and secondary materials [6–12].

Recent research into MOC generally revolves around its main disadvantage, poor water resistance. In recent experiments, it was shown, that in the pure state, MOC manifests quite a rapid loss of strength when exposed to water for a long period of time [13]. Zhang et al. conducted an experiment, in which they showed, that MOC phase 5 retains only approximately 9.2% of its original compressive strength after 28-day immersion in water [14]. The loss of strength is caused by the continuous transformation of MOC to

Fig. 5. Diffraction patterns of prepared composites.

flaky $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ (brucite), which results in the breakage of the microstructural skeleton of the material [15]. To model the outdoor environment of the application of MOC, Chang et al. used dry-wet cycling. In this experiment the deterioration of the mechanical parameters of the samples was somewhat delayed due to partial water evaporation during the dry phase of the cycle, however, the decrease was still quite significant [16]. To solve the problem of water-induced damage, researchers studied the application of func-

Fig. 6. SEM micrographs of prepared composites.

Table 3

Chemical composition in wt.% of M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS according to EDS.

Sample	C	O	Mg	Cl	Si	Al
M-REF	10.1	42.0	29.7	17.6	0.6	–
M-CNT	11.3	46.5	25.3	12.7	4.2	–
M-CNT-Ox	10.4	46.1	27.3	12.7	3.5	–
M-GO	12.5	46.3	24.8	11.7	4.7	–
M-G	11.7	46.4	26.2	12.6	3.1	–
M-ANS	15.9	45.9	19.7	8.2	9.6	0.7

tional additives in the form of inorganic and mineral admixtures, such as phosphoric acid, soluble phosphates, hydroxyacetic acid, fly ash, or gypsum [17–23]. These additives help to improve the water resistance, however, they also bring some unwanted side effects, such as hydration retardation, cracking, and formation of defects, and also decreased mechanical parameters of the prepared composite compared to reference composite prepared without the addition of functional additives [24].

The use of nanomaterials in cement-based construction composites is a quite pronounced topic in the research of novel building materials. The application of graphene was proven to accelerate the early-stage hydration, reduce the total porosity and pore diameter, significantly increase the values of mechanical parameters, improve durability and water resistance, and provide further specific properties, such as increased thermal and electrical conductivity [25–27]. The incorporation of the oxidized analogue of graphene, graphene/graphite oxide, shows similar results to graphene, with the advantage of simpler dispersion, as graphene oxide manifests the presence of oxygen-containing functional groups, which are hydrophilic [28–30]. Carbon nanotubes and their oxidized analogues were proven to be beneficial for the mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties as well as microstructure improvement in the case of their sufficient dispersion and mitigation of their agglomeration [31–34]. Except for the carbon-based nanomaterials, also other types of nanomaterials, such as alumina nanosheets were investigated for their possible use in construction composites. Feng et al. studied magnesium phosphate cement with the addition of alumina nanosheets showing that in an amount of 2.0–8.0 wt% it can significantly improve the workability of the mortar and the mechanical properties of the resulting composite [35]. Furthermore, it was previously proved, that nanosized alumina can help to mitigate the chloride-based degradation of cementitious composites, which results in their increased durability [36]. Alumina nanosheets were also proven to increase the strength retention rate after water immersion, which is crucial for alternative types of eco-friendly cement [37].

The changes in the microstructure of cementitious composites occurring after the introduction of nanomaterials are based on their structure, size and shape, as well as the properties of other used reinforcing agents, which are interlocked or interfacially embedded

Fig. 7. Detailed SEM micrographs of M-REF, M-CNT and M-CNT-Ox including EDS maps.

(inlaid) in the cement matrix [38,39]. For example, shorter carbon nanotubes disperse more uniformly in the cement paste and provide higher inter-bridging of the matrix microstructure [38]. On the other hand, the diameter of the carbon nanotubes contributes to the improvement of the cementitious microstructure to a much lesser extent [40]. Hydroxyl groups present in graphene oxide interact with C–S–H and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the cement matrix, resulting in improved strength due to the formation of hydration products among 3D interlocked graphene oxide sheets. This reduces the amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and the formation of the interfacial transition zone [41,42]. Graphene oxide was found to positively regulate the growth of C–S–H, thus reducing the pore diameter and the potential to propagate cracks [43].

Concerning the application of nanomaterials in MOC-based composites, the use of various carbon-based nano-dopants and their combinations was previously studied, showing their positive effect on the mechanical, structural, thermal and hygric properties [44–47].

This paper presents a comparative study of MOC modified with different types of nanosized additives, namely graphene, graphene oxide, multi-walled carbon nanotubes, oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes and alumina nanosheets. For each of the nano-dopants, its influence on micro- and macrostructural, mechanical, and hygric parameters is evaluated, with a special accent on the water resistance of the resulting composite, expressed in terms of softening coefficient after 24 h long immersion in water. Such a comprehensive analysis of the effect of nano-dopants on the properties and durability of MOC composites has not been presented before and represents a further step in the design and development of advanced types of reactive magnesia-based materials for the construction industry. Since the main deficiency of MOC is its poor water resistance, the presented research focused on the elimination of this deficiency by the use of nano-dopants, whose popularity in improving the performance of building materials is currently increasing and will continue in the near future. Moreover, the nano-dopants have demonstrated their ability to improve other material prop-

Fig. 8. Detailed SEM micrographs of M-GO, M-G and M-ANS including FDS maps.

erties, such as mechanical resistance, stiffness, and solidification, which will allow to obtain MOC composites with superior parameters and functionality.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and sample preparation

Table 1 provides the composition of each prepared composite based on magnesium oxychloride cement phase 5 (M). The 98% pure MgO powder was obtained from Penta, s.r.o., Prague, Czech Republic. The p.a. purity $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was sourced from Lach-ner, s.r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic. Filtrační písky spol. s r. o., Chlum u Doks, Czech Republic, provided silica sand in three different size fractions, namely PG1, PG2, and PG3 with particle sizes 0.0–0.5 mm, 0.5–1.0 mm and 1.0–2.0 mm, respectively. As nano-dopants multi-walled carbon nanotubes, oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, graphene, and alumina nanosheets were used. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CN1) and oxidized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (CNT-Ox) with purity > 95% were purchased from Chengdu Organic Chemicals Co. Ltd., Chinese Academy of Sciences (Chengdu, China). Industrial grade graphene oxide (GO) was obtained from ACS Material LLC, Pasadena, USA. Grade C graphene nanoplatelets (G) with a declared surface area of $750 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ were purchased from Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany. Alumina nanosheets (ANS) were obtained from Sawyer Technical Materials, LLC, Eastlake, USA as $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ polymorphic phase and purity > 95%. For all samples, tap water was used.

A reference material, named M-REF, was prepared without any nano-dopants as a point of comparison. The composite samples, namely M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G, and M-ANS, contained their corresponding nano-dopants in a quantity of 1.0 wt%, relative

Fig. 9. XRD pattern of M-REF-W, M-CNT-W, M-CNT-Ox-W, M-GO-W, M-G-W and M-ANS-W after 24h in water.

to the weight of the cement paste. The samples of the modified composites were designated according to the abbreviations for the individually applied nano-dopants, which are given above.

For the preparation of M-REF samples, crystalline $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was diluted in tap water and combined with MgO powder and silica sand using an automatic planetary-type mortar mixer. In the case of MOC-based composites with nano-dopants, the process involved diluting $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in tap water and mixing it with the respective nanomaterial using the Ultra-Turrax T-15 mechanical homoge-

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs of samples after immersion at various magnifications after 24h in water.

Table 4

Basic physical and hygric parameters of M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS, ρ_b is bulk density, ρ_s specific density, φ open porosity, W_{e24} 24-h water absorption.

Sample	ρ_s ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	ρ_b ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	φ (%)	W_{e24} ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	W_{e24} relative to reference (%)
M-REF	2061 ± 29	2269 ± 27	9.17 ± 0.18	63.6	–
M-CNT	2065 ± 29	2272 ± 27	9.11 ± 0.18	56.8	89.3
M-CNT-Ox	2032 ± 28	2268 ± 27	10.35 ± 0.21	53.7	84.4
M-GO	2060 ± 29	2266 ± 27	9.10 ± 0.18	53.0	83.3
M-G	2063 ± 29	2267 ± 27	8.99 ± 0.18	51.5	81.0
M-ANS	2056 ± 29	2271 ± 27	9.46 ± 0.19	58.4	91.8

nizer from IKA, Staufen, Germany. The homogenization was carried out for 5 min at a speed of 12,000 rpm. Afterwards, the suspension was mixed with MgO powder and silica sand in the planetary-type mortar mixer, similarly to the reference mixture. The resulting wet mixtures were transferred into prismatic moulds with dimensions of $40 \times 40 \times 160$ mm. Subsequently, the obtained prisms were demoulded after 1 day and left to cure on air for 27 days at a temperature of (23 ± 2) °C and a relative humidity of $(50 \pm 5)\%$.

2.2. Performed analyses and tests

The purchased nano-dopants were initially examined for their microstructure and chemical composition using techniques such as TEM, SEM, EDS, and gas adsorption analysis. Following this, the microstructure, chemical composition, mechanical properties, and hygric parameters of the prepared cement samples were studied. SEM, EDS, XRD, and FT-IR analyses were employed for this purpose. The focus of the analyses was on key properties of the samples, including bulk and matrix density, total open porosity, pore size distribution and corresponding microstructural parameters, as well as mechanical properties such as flexural and compressive strength, dynamic modulus of elasticity, water absorption after 24 h and softening coefficient, which was determined for samples immersed for 24 h in water. Samples immersed in water for 24 h were termed M-REF-W, M-CNT-W, M-CNT-Ox-W, M-GO-W, M-G-W, and M-ANS-W.

2.3. Analysis of nano-dopants

Purchased raw nano-dopants were analysed using TEM, SEM, EDS, and gas adsorption analysis. According to SEM and TEM (see Fig. 1) all nano-dopants showed their characteristic structure and size. CNT and CNT-Ox showed typical very long carbon tubes with a diameter of approximately 100 nm. In the SEM micrographs, GO and G appeared bulky, but upon closer examination using TEM at

Fig. 11. Total open porosity of M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS.

Fig. 12. Pore size distribution M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS: a) cumulative curves; b) incremental curves.

higher magnification, their layered structure became apparent. ANS exhibited a flake-like shape and revealed a layered microstructure. Elemental maps displayed in Fig. 2 obtained by EDS showed impurities in very minuscule concentrations, the quantity of each observed element is provided in Table 2. The presence of Ni impurities within carbon nanotubes (CNT's) can be attributed as a relic from the production process - gas catalytic decomposition of hydrocarbons over a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst. In GO, impurities (S, Mn and K) also come from the synthesis – namely from H₂SO₄ and KMnO₄. The presence of O in graphene nanoplatelets is most probably connected with the production process where graphene nanoplatelets are often produced through oxidation and exfoliation of graphite using oxygen-containing functional groups. Lastly, the C impurities in ANS are probably a result of manufacturing raw boehmite that can contain low carbon concentrations.

The surface area of each nano-dopant was evaluated using gas adsorption analysis, employing the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory. Among the nano-dopants, G exhibited the highest surface area of approximately 653.49 m² g⁻¹. Notably, CNT-Ox displayed a higher surface area of 109.78 m² g⁻¹ compared to CNT, which registered a surface area of 96.36 m² g⁻¹. This disparity can be attributed to the oxidation process, which leads to the partial or complete opening of carbon nanotubes. Conversely, ANS exhibited the lowest surface area of approximately 11.35 m² g⁻¹. Sorption isotherms can be found in Supporting Information - Fig. SI 1.

3. Results and discussion

The reference and nano-doped composite samples were prepared according to the method described above. All prepared composite samples were characterized and compared after 28 days of curing in a stable environment. The prepared cement samples in the form of prisms are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 13. Volumetric representation of pores according to their diameter.

Table 5
Microstructural parameters of M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS.

Sample	η_{H_2} (%)	Average pore diameter (μm)	Total pore volume (cm^3g^{-1})
M-REF	9.57	0.0464	0.0468
M-CNT	9.87	0.0451	0.0442
M-CNT-Ox	10.21	0.0494	0.0516
M-GO	8.99	0.0467	0.0455
M-G	8.90	0.0471	0.0469
M-ANS	9.99	0.0470	0.0550

Table 6
Relative intruded volume and relative porosity corresponding to diameter range of capillary pores identified in M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS samples.

Capillary pores								
Pore size	0.0025 < d < 0.01 μm		0.01 < d < 0.1 μm		0.1 < d < 10 μm		d^{a} > 10 μm	
Role of water	Water – strong surface tension forces		High effect on vapour transport, moderate surface tension forces		Bulk water – high effect on capillarity		Do not affect water transport, influence vapour transmission	
Sample	Relative volume intruded (cm^3g^{-1})	Relative porosity (%)	Relative volume intruded (cm^3g^{-1})	Relative porosity (%)	Relative volume intruded (cm^3g^{-1})	Relative porosity (%)	Relative volume intruded (cm^3g^{-1})	Relative porosity (%)
M-REF	–	–	0.0389	83.08	0.0073	15.60	0.0006	1.32
M-CNT	–	–	0.0363	82.14	0.0052	11.70	0.0027	6.14
M-CNT-Ox	0.0003	0.52	0.0324	62.81	0.0151	29.17	0.0038	7.26
M-GO	0.0001	0.08	0.0372	81.83	0.0075	16.4	0.0008	1.68
M-G	0.0001	0.26	0.0364	77.49	0.0092	19.62	0.0012	2.63
M-ANS	–	–	0.0469	85.29	0.0081	14.72	–	–

^a d = pore diameter.

3.1. Morphology, chemical and phase composition

The prepared samples were crushed, and the fracture surface was examined using an optical microscope. The resulting micrographs (see Fig. 4) showed very similar surface morphology for all samples except for the colour, which is dependent on the colour of the nano-dopant. It is noteworthy that the distribution of silica sand appears to be uniform across all the samples.

Phase composition analysis conducted using XRD confirmed the presence of two distinct phases in all the prepared samples. The first identified phase was MOC phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ICDD 00-007-0420) [48], while the second detected phase was SiO_2 (ICDD 01-075-8322) [49], originating from the silica sand used as a filler. This XRD analysis substantiates the consistent presence of these phases across all the prepared samples as can be seen from Fig. 5.

Fig. 14. Mechanical parameters of prepared samples.

SEM analysis was used to examine the surface morphology of all prepared samples on the fracture surface. The micrographs presented in Fig. 6 revealed no observable cracks or defects in the microstructure of the samples. Each sample displayed the characteristic presence of elongated needle-shaped crystals of MOC Phase 5, with dimensions between 2 and 10 μm in length and approximately 0.5 μm in width. Unfortunately, at this stage of magnification and sample preparation, it was not possible to observe whole MOC crystals as they are embedded and intercalated in the precipitated MOC matrix. Due to the small size of the nano-dopants, no apparent differences in surface morphology were observed at this level of magnification. However, it is assumed that the MOC matrix envelops the nanoparticles which, due to their different structure, size and shape, can affect the formed MOC matrix in different ways. On the other hand, elemental maps derived from EDS analysis (see SI Fig. SI 2, SI 3) confirmed that nano-dopants were uniformly distributed throughout the samples, resulting in minimal disparities in the microstructure. The obtained elemental composition from EDS is presented in Table 3.

A detailed SEM analysis in combination with EDS mapping in high-resolution mode of the MOC composites showed how different nano-dopants were emplaced in the MOC matrix (see Figs. 7 and 8). The M-REF sample consisted of two typical shapes of MOC needle-like crystals – thick and short; thin and long. The CNT and CNT-Ox nanoparticles were quite agglomerated and created bundles where MOC crystal grew in between long carbon nanotubes. Around the bundles of nanotubes, majorly thick and short MOC crystals were formed, whereas the MOC crystals grown through the nanotube bundles were mainly thin and long. The agglomeration of nanotubes was caused by insufficient homogenization, which could have been avoided by longer homogenization of their dispersion by ultrasonic needle or by the addition of surfactants preventing their re-agglomeration after homogenization for a shorter period of time. In the M-GO sample, MOC crystals did not go straight through GO sheets and created a cavity around the top and bottom of the sheet, whereas the edges of the GO sheet were strongly attached to the MOC matrix with a very dense structure of thick and very short MOC crystals. The graphene nanoplatelets in the M-G sample were agglomerated in bigger sphere-shaped structures (approximately 2 μm in diameter) that were surrounded by short and thick MOC crystals, some of which grew through the graphene sphere-shaped structure – supposedly between individual graphene sheets. The ANS particles in M-ANS were surrounded by long MOC crystals where none went through the ANS particles, the MOC crystals intergrew together on the surface of ANS particles.

Following a 24-h immersion in water, the prepared samples underwent XRD analysis to assess any potential changes in phase composition. As depicted in Fig. 9, the XRD patterns revealed that the phase composition remained unchanged after contact with water. In all samples, only two phases were detected: SiO_2 (ICDD 01-075-8322) and $\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (ICDD 00-007-0420). These findings indicate that the identified phases remained stable and unaffected by the water immersion.

After water immersion, an examination of the microstructure changes was carried out, as depicted in Fig. 10. The obtained SEM micrographs show silica sand particles, characteristic individual needle-like crystals of Phase 5, and dense aggregates of MOC crystals where individual needles were indistinguishable. In the case of MOC composites with nano-dopants, the individual nano-dopant particles were not visually discernible. However, EDS analysis confirmed a relatively uniform distribution of nano-dopant elements across the samples, thereby validating their homogeneous dispersion. For visual reference, EDS elemental maps can be found in SI (Fig. SI 5, SI 6).

Fig. 15. M-REF, M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G and M-ANS: a) residual compressive strength; b) softening coefficient.

3.2. Macro- and microstructural parameters, hygric properties

The basic physical parameters of the 28-day composites are shown in Table 4. Porosity values are also provided in graphical form for better visualization (Fig. 11). The presented data represent mean values from the measurement of three samples and are presented including the expanded combined uncertainty of the performed tests. Except for the M-CNT-Ox samples, the use of nano-dopants had no apparent effect on the obtained values of bulk density, specific density and open porosity. The differences between the investigated materials were typically in the range of measurement uncertainty. On the other hand, the decrease in bulk density and the related increase in porosity of the MOC composites with the oxidized carbon nanotubes were evident, but still not significant enough to negatively affect the material properties and durability. Quantitatively, the increase in the total open porosity was approx. 12.9 % compared to the control sample M-REF.

The microstructure of hardened composites was analysed by Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP). Cumulative and incremental pore size distribution curves are graphed in Fig. 12a and b. The pore volume fraction corresponding to the specific pore diameter range is presented in Fig. 13. The microstructural parameters obtained by MIP are summarized in Table 5. The total pore volume varied, the average pore diameter and φ_{TIG} (total open porosity measured by MIP) were the highest for composite M-CNT-Ox, which is in accordance with above-presented macrostructural parameters. Slightly increased pore structure characteristics were also identified for composite with alumina nanosheets. In Fig. 12, the increase in the pore volume fraction for pores in the 1–100 μm range was apparent for the M-CNT-Ox composite.

Since the improvement of the water resistance of MOC through the use of selected nano-dopants was the main objective of the presented research, the results of the pore size distribution are presented in terms of the relative volume intruded and the relative porosity corresponding to the range of diameter of the capillary pores observed in the studied samples. These data are presented in Table 6,

Fig. 16. NIR spectrum of MOC composites: a) laboratory-cured samples and b) samples immersed for 24 h in water.

and the effect of the pore size on the moisture transport mechanisms is also introduced. The highest relative porosity affecting the capillary moisture transport was revealed for the M-CNT-Ox sample, which was well documented by the measured pore size distribution and cumulative curves given above. From a structural point of view, the composite with the oxidized carbon nanotubes should facilitate water transport the most among the tested materials. However, this was not the case. All composites modified with nanodopants exhibited considerably lower water absorption compared to the reference sample M-REF (Table 4). The lowest 24-h water absorption value ($W_{a24} = 551.5 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) was obtained for the M-G composite. The decrease in the water absorption varied in the range of 81.0–91.8%. This was attributed to the typical hydrophobic nature of carbon-based nano-dopants [50,51], which hinders their dispersion in solvents and leads to their agglomeration. The hydrophobic nature significant for Al_2O_3 [52] competed with slightly higher porosity and pore parameters of M-ANS during water ingress. In this case, the reduction in 24-h water absorption was 91.8%. In principle, the hydrophobicity and impermeability of the used nano-dopants were the dominant parameters influencing the overall decrease of the water transport ability of the nano-modified composites, which is a very promising result for the improvement of their durability, since the reduced water absorption prevents the water-induced crack propagation and structural disintegration. Based on the obtained results of 24-h water absorption it is obvious that the effect of the hydrophobic nature of the used nano-dopants on moisture transport was dominant over the differences in porosity and pore size distribution.

Table 7

Assignments of the major absorption bands of MOC composites.

Wavenumbers cm^{-1}	Assignment
3694	stretching (ν) vibration of O–H in $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$
3648, 3612	stretching (ν) vibration of II-O-II in $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
3390, 3380	stretching (ν) vibration of H–O–H in H_2O
1600, 1165	bending (δ) vibration of H–O–H in $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
1525, 1446	stretching (ν) vibration of Mg–O in $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
1608	stretching (ν) vibration of C = C
1165	stretching (ν) vibration of Mg–O in $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$
1090	stretching (ν) vibration of Si–O in sand
788	stretching (ν) vibration of Mg–O cubic structure
688	stretching (ν) vibrations of Mg–O
592	deformation (δ) and stretching (ν) lattice vibrations of Mg–Cl/Mg–O
457	vibrational modes of the lattice showing the Mg–O/ Mg^{2+} , O/O–Mg–O/O– Mg^{2+} –O bonds

3.3. Mechanical parameters

The mechanical parameters of the composites are presented in Fig. 14. With the exception of M-ANS, the compressive strength of the composites containing nano-dopants was improved. The highest increase in compressive strength was obtained with the use of CNT-Ox and GO. The improvement was 6.1% (~85.0 MPa) and 5.3% (~84.4 MPa), respectively. This suggests that oxidation improved the incorporation of the selected nano-dopants in the MOC matrix, resulting in the formation of a more compact structure of the composites, which were thus able to withstand higher compressive forces. The incorporation of nano-dopants also resulted in increased flexural strength. The highest values of flexural strength were obtained for the composites with CNT-Ox and ANS. Except for the excellent flexural strength and stiffness of these nano-dopants themselves [53,54], the long oxidized carbon tubes and flake-shaped alumina caused such significant enhancement of flexural strength, which was approx. 48.4% (~19.8 MPa) for M-CNT-Ox and 57.0% (~21.0 MPa) for M-ANS. Li et al. presented cement mortars (from Ordinary Portland cement) with oxidized carbon nanotubes where the flexural and compressive strength had risen to ~8.1 MPa, and to ~54.1 MPa, respectively with the addition of CNT-Ox [55]. Compared to the observed effect of the specific nano-dopant on mechanical strength, the differences in the dynamic modulus of elasticity were minimal and varied in the 1.6–3.0% range. This corresponds to the expanded combined uncertainty of the dynamic Young's modulus assessment.

3.4. Water resistance

The effect of incorporated nano-dopants on the durability of MOC composites against water-induced damage was characterized by the assessment of softening coefficient α_s (%), which was calculated as a ratio of the residual compressive strength of the laboratory-cured samples after 24-h immersion in water and the compressive strength before the immersion. In the durability assessment, the softening coefficient was considered a key parameter of the researched composites' resistance against water damage. The residual compressive strength and softening coefficient values are reported in Fig. 15a and b. When assessing the softening coefficient and residual compressive strength data, it is important to realize that in practice, such extreme moisture exposure will rarely occur. The durability of MOC composites against deterioration in water was improved by all examined nano-dopants. The softening coefficient determined for samples immersed in water for 24 h varied from 62.7 to 74.8%. The best resistance to water disruption was achieved for M-ANS, which exhibited a softening coefficient value about 23.2% higher compared to that of the reference sample M-REF. Although the use of alumina nanosheets partially reduced the compressive strength of the hardened composites, the significantly increased flexural strength, stiffness and water resistance make this nano-dopant effective for the improvement of the MOC matrix as it helps to at least partially mitigate the biggest lack of MOC, which is its vulnerability to water. The CNT-Ox improved the softening coefficient to a smaller extent (by 11.7%) but with a positive effect on the compressive and flexural strength, which were increased by approx. 6.1% and 48.4%, respectively. At this stage of research, these two nano-dopants were identified as prospective dopants for MOC.

The chemical structure changes due to water-induced damage of MOC composites were observed using Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy. Fig. 16a and b shows the NIR spectra recorded for the MOC composites with the nano-dopants and the reference before and after immersion in water for 24 h. All the analysed samples can be characterised by the main absorption bands, the assignment of which is summarized in Table 7. The broad absorption band with a maximum of 3380 cm^{-1} (a) and 3390 cm^{-1} (b) reflects vibrations of H–O in water typical for the MOC phase 5. The main difference between laboratory-cured samples and samples immersed in water for 24 h represents a strong absorption band at 3694 cm^{-1} . This unique peak can be assigned to the stretching vibrations of O–H in brucite thus calculation of the content of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ in tested MOC composites according to the Lambert-Beer law can be applied [47]. The calculated relative brucite content was 0.17, 0.10, 0.11, 0.13, 0.26 and 0.20 for M-CNT, M-CNT-Ox, M-GO, M-G, M-ANS, and M-REF, respectively. The calculated relative amount of brucite corresponds well with the tested mechanical properties as with the increasing content of brucite the mechanical strength decreases. The absorption bands around 2000 cm^{-1} arise due to O–H bonds bending and rocking vibrations contribution. The MOC phase 5 was formed and thus the characteristic absorption band at 1165 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the stretching vibration of Mg–O in $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is present. To observe the presence of carbon nano-dopants the peak resolution was performed and a weak band at 1608 cm^{-1} was identified and can be attributed to the stretching vibration of the C = C bond. Around 1090 cm^{-1} intense absorption bands can be attributed to stretching vibrations of Si–O from the

sand aggregate. Below 700 cm^{-1} in the absorption spectrum the characteristic deformation, stretching, and translation vibration of Mg–O and Mg–Cl bonds in the $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ lattice can be observed.

4. Conclusion

A comparative study on the novel approach to modification of MOC-based composites via nano-doping by various types of nano-dopants was conducted. MOC composites incorporating silica sand filler and various nano-dopants in the amount of 1.0 wt% relative to the cement paste weight were prepared and examined. The investigation focused on evaluating the impact of nano-dopants on various material properties, including micro- and macrostructural parameters, mechanical characteristics, and hygric properties, with a particular emphasis on durability following water immersion assessment. To provide a base for comparison, the outcomes of M-NANO composites were analysed alongside a reference M-REF sample without any nano-dopant. The effect of the nano-dopants on the properties of the MOC-based composites is summarized in the following points:

- (i) The addition of the nano-dopants into the cement matrix did not have a significant effect on the bulk density, specific density and open porosity of the composites, except for CNT-Ox where the bulk density was lower and open porosity was increased by 12.9% compared to M-REF. This effect can be caused by agglomeration of the nanotubes. For other samples, the macrostructural parameter values varied within the standard deviation range.
- (ii) The mechanical properties were enhanced in all measured parameters (compressive strength, dynamic Young's modulus and flexural strength) for all nano-dopants, except for M-ANS where the compressive strength was decreased by 3.9%. The highest compressive strength value of 85.04 MPa was measured for M-CNT-Ox, which was 6.1% higher than the control composite M-REF. M-ANS achieved the best values for flexural strength and Young's modulus of 20.99 MPa and 38.55 GPa, respectively.
- (iii) The key observed parameter in this contribution, the water resistance of the prepared composites, was evaluated in the form of softening coefficient. The softening coefficient values were noticeably increased in M-ANS and M-CNT-Ox by 23.2% and 11.7% compared to M-REF, respectively. For other nano-doped samples, the increase in this parameter was present, but not as significant.

The vision for this study was to emphasize the impact of various nanomaterials as nano-dopants in cement composites based on reactive magnesia. Based on the achieved results, positive influence of the nanomaterials used as functional additives for the improvement of mechanical properties and water resistance of MOC composites was proved and classified as highly effective. As alumina nanosheets proved to be efficient in water resistance improvement and their incorporation into the MOC matrix represents an interesting and prospective system, future research will deal with different amounts of ANS and explore the potential benefits of combining ANS with other nanomaterials. This approach aims to create the best possible material by harnessing the synergistic effect of different types of nanomaterials.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Adéla Jiříčková: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Michal Lojka:** Investigation. **Martina Záleská:** Investigation. **Adam Pivák:** Investigation. **Milena Pavlíková:** Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation. **Alexandra Merglová:** Investigation. **Zbyšek Pavlík:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2024.108981>.

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